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Editors' note

In the meaning closest to its etymology, literacy is a practice associated with everything a person must do to read and write. Today, the concept has transcended reading and writing skills and has expanded to encompass other essential skills for building knowledge by a person or a community. In this sense, sustainability literacy seeks to create and use knowledge to act in the face of the socio-environmental challenges in which we are immersed and involves the assimilation of key concepts on these topics, the critical analysis of the challenges associated with people-nature interactions, and the adoption of new paradigms that promote individual and collective agency in the care of our common home, our planet.

In this issue, Yamilet Morales addresses literacy as a path to new forms of teaching, dissemination, participation, and empowerment. For his part, Flover Rodríguez, Executive Director of the Colombian Association of Energy Geologists and Geophysicists (ACGGP), delves into the important role of the dissemination of geological knowledge in the formation of a more conscious, resilient, and strengthened society for decision-making about its territory. In the *CO₂NVERSING* section, María José García and Nicole Mellado, from the El Árbol Foundation, share their experiences on experiential learning in community projects for the formulation of responses and solutions to the socio-environmental crises in Chile. In the *Yes, yes it is* section, we have included an infographic on the pillars of education and another on literacy in the educational field. In the *Take Away* section, we share some resources, books, video games, and documentaries to reflect on several of the topics presented in this edition.

A photograph of a simple, weathered wooden chair with a flat back and four legs, sitting on a concrete surface. The background is a lush green field with some cows grazing in the distance, under a clear sky with some trees and hills in the far background.

LITERACY: TEACHING, DISSEMINATING, PARTICIPATING AND EMPOWERING

By Yamilet Morales Fuentes

Literacy, in its most complex sense, transcends the mere acquisition of basic reading and writing skills, as it has been traditionally treated under the term "*literacy*." According to Blandón-Ramírez and Colombo (2024), literacy was long understood as a set of skills that developed independently of the sociocultural context of individuals. This view has been expanded and challenged by research recognizing the diversity of reading and writing practices in different communities and forms of knowledge, highlighting how culture and environment directly influence their development. Thus, literacy, unlike literacy, is a social practice shaped by cultural and contextual factors.

This concept, introduced in the Latin American context as a translation of the Anglo-Saxon term literacy, exceeds the limited notions of literacy since it implies the comprehensive development of oral and written skills in different sociocultural contexts, which allows for the expansion of learning processes (Riquelme Arredondo & Quintero Corzo, 2018). Beyond a technical skill, literacy is a living practice that requires new forms of teaching and dissemination familiar to the people it addresses and adapted to the diverse contexts in which people operate.

Furthermore, literacy encompasses the use and development of oral and written language in a dynamic and multifaceted manner, which requires a more inclusive pedagogy based on the sociocultural reality of people. UNESCO (2006) supports this perspective, emphasizing that literacy is constantly redefined and influenced by personal experiences, cultural values, and educational policies.

While literacy is closely linked to education, it also represents a fundamental tool for social and political participation. This perspective resonates with the constructivist tradition, where learning is conceived as a process in which the subject is an active agent of their formation (Riquelme Arredondo & Quintero Corzo, 2018). Through this approach, literacy becomes a powerful mechanism for social transformation and the empowerment of communities. In line with the constructivist vision, which proposes the emergence of learning from social interaction, experiences, and reflection around them (Ortiz Granja, 2015), literacy in sustainability issues is a practice and an exercise that involves the construction of meanings from the connection with the natural and social environment.

Blandón-Ramírez and Colombo (2024) highlight how hybrid literacy practices allow for the creation of transdisciplinary work and publications that reflect the voices of communities, contributing to greater visibility and empowerment of the most vulnerable and limited people to participate in knowledge production processes. This transdisciplinary approach is especially relevant to addressing socio-environmental problems, given the variety of actors who share common objectives, such as the defense of the territory or the search for more sustainable paths. This wealth of knowledge and perspectives offers both opportunities and challenges in the context of literacy since one of the main challenges to building knowledge from an interactoral process is the formation of an extended peer community (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993), whose objective is the joint delimitation of the problem and the formation of a collaborative work team in which rules and responsibilities are assigned that lead to the co-production of knowledge.

Although integrating diverse actors and forms of knowledge can be complex, good coordination will generate more inclusive and representative responses, increasing participation and the impact of the proposed solutions. This plurality will also enrich knowledge creation, making it more durable because different ways of understanding, organizing, and communicating problems and their possible solutions will be considered. Thus, the transdisciplinary approach not only facilitates the comprehensive understanding of socio-environmental problems but also promotes a collaborative process that recognizes the diversity of experiences and knowledge as a strength for joint action.

Another function of literacy is disseminating knowledge, especially in social and collaborative research that focuses on working with communities. An example of this approach is the Signos Vitales initiative, promoted by a network of community foundations in Mexico, whose objective is to collect and organize the knowledge and information dispersed among the various actors in a community. The key to this project lies in recognizing the value and strengths that already exist in these communities to promote their collective development. To achieve this, they actively involve people in identifying their experiences, strengths, opportunities, challenges, and needs in social, political, economic, and environmental issues (González-Ulloa & Morales, 2024).

As regards disseminating knowledge about literacy, in addition to focusing on traditional academic spaces, it must also do so in communities and local contexts to generate new collaborative approaches to producing knowledge (Blandón-Ramírez & Colombo, 2024). In this way, the active role of people in the construction and dissemination of knowledge is recognized, as well as respecting cultural diversity and promoting the integral development of human capacities. Thus, we have a key element for critical and participatory education, facilitating access to knowledge and social transformation.

In the context of sustainability, the dissemination of knowledge must convey a kind of “minimum requirement,” – which leads to the understanding that current challenges – biodiversity loss, environmental injustice, climate change, eutrophication, and climate migration, among others – are interconnected, both temporally and spatially. The problems we face are intergenerational, and although they may originate in local contexts, there is a constant relationship of influence and feedback between the local and the global. Thus, dissemination in sustainability is critical to generating awareness and collective action that emanates from this interdependence.

Finally, empowerment through literacy allows individuals and communities to become agents of change, capable of influencing the structural and systemic factors that limit a direct relationship with the socio-environmental problems they face. In this sense, participatory methodologies reveal how literacy can be a driving force for social transformation, promoting the creation of collaborative projects aimed at the common good, changing power structures, and caring for the environment.

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THE POWER OF DISSEMINATING GEOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE IN COLOMBIA:

A PATH TOWARDS CLIMATE ADAPTATION AND SOCIAL INCLUSION

By **Flover Rodríguez-Portillo**
Executive Director
Colombian Association of Energy Geologists
and Geophysicists, ACGGP

Geology is the science that studies the Earth, its processes and resources, and is fundamental to understanding our natural environment. In a country like Colombia, with an impressive geological diversity ranging from the Andes mountain range to vast plains and coasts, the dissemination of geological knowledge has a transformative power. This dissemination can significantly contribute to democratizing knowledge, generating awareness about the territories we inhabit, and strengthening various social actors' capacities. Below, we explore these three objectives and how to achieve them through an appropriate strategy of dissemination and construction of knowledge through the Regional Pedagogy Program of the Colombian Association of Energy Geologists and Geophysicists (ACGGP).

Democratization of Geological Knowledge

Traditionally, geological knowledge has been reserved for academics and professionals in the sector, creating a barrier between science and society. However, democratizing this knowledge allows communities to better understand their territories' resources and risks. There is no better way to inhabit, protect, and manage a territory than knowing it in detail. To achieve this, it is necessary to develop accessible communication tools, from educational materials in schools to outreach campaigns in digital media and community workshops, as well as joint work with local, regional, and national government administrative authorities.

The Colombian Geological Service (SGC) is responsible for conducting research and monitoring geological threats in the country, including landslides. In 2015, it published an update to the National Map of Relative Threat from Mass Movements at a scale of 1:100,000, from which approximately 50% of the national territory was categorized as a low threat, 22% as a medium threat, 20% as a high threat, and 4% as a very high threat due to mass movements. The work showed that this type of information must be accessible so that communities know how to act in time in the face of geological risks.

Likewise, initiatives such as itinerant geology museums or field days open to the public can help citizens understand the importance of geological resources. For example, the National Geological Museum "José Royo y Gómez" receives around 12,000 visitors annually, which shows society's interest in learning about geology. These activities contribute to the expansion of knowledge and to overcoming academic barriers by making this valuable information available to everyone.

With the above in mind, we can then say that the democratization of knowledge implies an inclusive approach, where we speak in simple language and value the diverse forms of knowledge of the communities. In addition, it is worth noting that the action takes place locally; it is the place from where we can transform ourselves together. Collective awareness can encourage better decision-making in the use and conservation of natural resources, such as the use of natural gas, a resource of which Colombia has proven reserves of 2.37 terabytes of cubic feet (Tcf) by 2023, according to the National Hydrocarbons Agency (ANH), as well as many other resources in our territories.

Awareness of the Geological Territories We Inhabit

Colombia is a country with a dynamic and diverse geography. Understanding local geology allows us to better appreciate our territories' risks and potential. Raising awareness about geological territories means that communities understand how landscapes were formed and what natural risks they are exposed to, in addition to contributing their own knowledge to the construction of adaptation strategies. This awareness is essential not only for the safety of the population but also for sustainable development.

In recent years, Colombia has experienced a significant number of geological phenomena, such as the earthquake in Armenia in 1999, which left more than 1,100 dead and thousands injured, or the flood in Mocoa, which left more than 300 dead and more than 400 injured. In the last 10 years, the country has had to invest more than 11 billion pesos in disaster relief due to natural phenomena. Knowing and understanding these events and the risks of landslides can save lives, protect infrastructure, and build sustainable territories.

From the perspective of new underground energy sources, the country's geothermal potential is significant: the SGC has identified more than 300 areas with geothermal manifestations, representing a key opportunity to sustainably generate renewable energy. Understanding the geothermal potential or the availability of aquifers in certain regions can open up new possibilities for local economic development. Geology, in this sense, becomes a tool to value and protect the environment, reduce vulnerability to natural disasters, and responsibly use the resources offered by the subsoil. For example, the underground water resource in Colombia represents around 25% of the country's total drinking water supply.

Strengthening capacities for a national strategy for adaptation to climate change

In the context of climate change, geological knowledge becomes crucial for designing adaptation strategies. Strengthening the capacities of social actors through geological dissemination means empowering communities, companies, and decision-makers with the information necessary to face the challenges brought by climate change. According to IDEAM, nearly 70% of natural disasters in Colombia are related to climatic phenomena, many of them associated with the geology of the territory. Capacity development should focus on creating a culture of resilience, where all actors understand the importance of the natural systems surrounding us and how we can adapt to their changes.

Capacity building involves training community leaders, educating public sector professionals, and promoting inter-institutional collaboration. In 2022, the country adopted the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan, the success of which will largely depend on the active participation and knowledge of local communities. Initiatives such as training in the management of groundwater resources, promoting the use of geothermal energy, and preparing for extreme geological phenomena are key to reducing risks and improving the quality of life of communities.

Knowledge that transforms

The dissemination of geological knowledge in Colombia is fundamental in building a more conscious, resilient, and equitable society. Democratizing this knowledge allows each individual to understand their environment better and actively participate in decision-making regarding using natural resources. By raising awareness about the territories and strengthening local capacities, we can build a national strategy for adaptation to climate change that considers the country's needs and realities. Ultimately, geological knowledge is an empowerment tool that can contribute to fairer and more sustainable development.

Since 2017, the ACGGP Regional Pedagogy Program has impacted more than 25,000 people in Colombia through different strategies, with the dialogue of knowledge as a work philosophy and designing methodologies that adapt to the particularities of the territories and their inhabitants. In this way, it has managed to be present in 22 departments of the country and nearly 100 municipalities. The Program has achieved coordination with local, regional, and national governments to design and execute pedagogical actions that strengthen the capacities of Colombian society. In this way, we build knowledge with and for people that allows them to participate and act in the face of the various phenomena and challenges we face.

Colombian Association of
Geologists and Energy
Geophysicists
<https://www.acggp.org/>

CONVERSING

From the roots to the construction of transformative knowledge

Interview with **María José García and Nicole Mellado.**
El Árbol Foundation

By **Jazmín Mota and Lorena Morales**

Promoting socio-environmental action and strengthening communities through their own experiences has transformative power. Thus, achieving long-lasting and sustainable transformations requires a deep connection between people and nature that allows us to see our own stories and experiences in others, in the other, and in everything else with which we relate and interact.

In this interview, we spoke with María José García and Nicole Mellado from the *El Árbol Foundation*. This organization was born in 2011 and established in 2013 to work on community projects to formulate responses and solutions to socio-environmental crises in Chile.

María José is the founder and executive director of the El Árbol Foundation. She is an architect with a master's degree in Architecture and Environment, a diploma in Sustainable Urbanism, a CEFE facilitator, and an outdoor environmental education facilitator.

Nicole is a project coordinator at the foundation. She is an environmental engineer with a diploma in geomatics applied to territorial planning and an environmental education facilitator.

We hope that you find this conversation motivating to transform the way you perceive and facilitate education beyond the classroom, as well as reinvent traditional ways of generating and sharing knowledge.

J: María José and Nicole, it is a pleasure to talk with you today. Could you tell us about yourselves and the El Árbol Foundation?

MJ: I am María José García, founder and current executive director of Fundación El Árbol. In 2010, the first seed of the foundation was planted, motivated by the desire to support those affected by the earthquake and tsunami that hit Chile that year. We started a tetrapack collection campaign that allowed us to insulate 500 emergency homes, where around 400 reused tetrapack tiles were installed. The number of people from all over Chile who participated was incredible, and we realized we could not stop something so beautiful.

This project benefited the environment and supported the communities, so we continued. Today, we work with the same approach, strengthening communities and promoting socio-environmental action to strengthen the territory and its protection. We do this through three fundamental lines of work: the first arose from the tetrapack campaign and became a waste management system that we now call “Recyclers;” The “Zero Waste” area focuses on generating experiences for people to reflect on how and why we generate waste, and how, through our actions, we can reduce it; the third is the “Ecosystems” area, focused on participatory and community restoration of the territory with the communities.

N: I joined the foundation as an intern in 2018, and today, I am the coordinator of the Ecosystems area. During the life of the foundation, we have been refining our approach to action, but we have worked in three areas. We realized that what unites us is education and

that we comprehensively address socio-environmental issues. We like the idea that humans are part of nature and intrinsically connected to it. Even though we live in cities, nature is always present; it is a network of interconnections.

Therefore, we decided to focus on regenerating that relationship between people and their environment by promoting actions that improve the well-being of nature and, in turn, human well-being. Our path starts with Chile’s people and communities facing climate crises and other issues like waste management. In the face of several crises, we think we need sustainable solutions that do not depend on the state. People often find themselves in a moment of need, and the only help comes from the State. People do not act from their own organization to respond to problems, and although obviously, this help is necessary, but once it ends, everything returns to normal.

So, we try to insert environmental awareness and actions into these life cycles in an organized and collective way that people can carry out from their own ancestral wisdom. Our purpose is community strengthening for the environment: to provide the tools, capabilities, opportunities, and necessary facilities so that, once we leave the place, the territory, the school, the neighborhood council, this human group, has the capacity to continue acting against the environmental problem.

That is where **environmental education** comes in. **It is our language**, a language that encourages participation, dialogue, and horizontality to recover ancient knowledge that already exists. We do not come with a position of "we have the solution;" instead, we believe that the solution is here, collective, and the communities must find and sustain it. For this reason, our educational approach is participatory or popular, focused on environmental education.

J: Returning to approaching communities, I think it is great to think of education as a language, not to impose ideas, but to build knowledge together. I would like to ask you how this fits in with the methodology on which your work is based and what kind of results you have obtained.

MJ: Our methodology is the *learning spiral*, an **experiential learning methodology** with four stages. The person lives an experience, then questions that experience reflects on it, acquires theoretical knowledge, and finally, the cycle closes with a new experience. It is a circle that can be repeated many times. The beauty of this methodology is that we can all contribute something because all experiences are unique and nourish us mutually as a community. This joint and individual experience strengthens the community and makes us learn more together. From there comes our vision of knowledge acquisition: **we all build and contribute to knowledge.**

N: We feed this methodological framework with different elements depending on where we are. We adapt the methodology to the site's historical and cultural context.

We want an environmental action to emerge from a strengthened community because if we deliver knowledge or tools in a unidirectional way when we leave the territory, people will not know what to do with it. So, it is not just about teaching the name of a tree or how to make compost at home; it is also about providing emotional and organizational tools so that they can keep it further.

There is a spark that occurs when moments of connection beyond rationality are achieved, when something reaches the emotion and meaning that allows knowledge not only to be understood but also to be felt, like a deep memory. It is like a "wow, I see this in this way! and another person sees it too," and there arises an opportunity for action through enriching moments that are built collectively. That is why I say how important the context is; we must know the realities of the people.

We cannot simply copy and paste the same workshop everywhere because each place may have special conditions we must know and adapt to. Our methodology must be prepared so that this moment of "wow!" occurs appropriately and allows for the validation of emotionality, individuality, and diversity so that people feel that what they are and what they know is valuable and part of a broader framework.

In Kolb's **experiential learning** methodology, which is our foundation, as María José said, we start with experience and then move on to reflection, which is a crucial moment of horizontal dialogue where we converse and analyze. Then comes conceptualization, ideally participatory, building concepts together. And finally, these concepts are validated with an activity or practical experience. This cycle can be applied on a large scale or in a short workshop, such as a one-hour virtual workshop.

We are also inspired by Paulo Freire's vision and his focus on **popular education**. We strongly believe in the power of play to help people lose their fear of making mistakes. That is why we use many games and dynamics that help build knowledge. Through play, we make people feel more comfortable; creativity flourishes if the fear of failing is reduced. We create an environment where people experiment, give their opinions, and are not afraid of making mistakes to generate a safe and participatory space where these magical learning moments occur.

J: I believe that recognizing our own experience and ourselves in the other person's experience is very powerful. Education should not only happen in the mind but should be experienced with the whole being: what you think, feel, smell, hear. I put a lot of emphasis on the fact that education should be loving, creative, and fun. Especially loving because, in many cases, exercising power through knowledge control does not allow for the connection we need to motivate action on issues such as socio-environmental ones.

I want to ask you about the Guide of Activities for Environmental Education you recently published. How did this valuable tool for the joint construction of knowledge come about?

N: This book is a dream we have had for a long time. Our activities are fueled by various sources: games we played as children, experiences as scouts, different training courses, etc., and activities that work with all ages, from children to adults.

The book brings together many of these ideas gathered after years of experience. We have been developing ideas fed by various projects' experiences. We worked with beekeepers, with a group that cultivated native flora, or with those who protect rivers. The idea was to form a community articulation so that people could take action. We identified almost 250 activities, including community dialogues called "mateadas" and "mingas". Minga is a concept used often here; it means getting together to do something. For example, the "*minga del vino*" (wine minga), where people gather to harvest grapes and make wine; there are mingas to move houses in some areas; people get together, take a house off its foundations, and move it completely.

The activities included many games and dynamics, both to start an activity and generate a learning environment and to activate people, collect shared memories, or make a plantation and seek a common goal. With all this, we said: "OK, let's compile and compact it so that other people can do their own activities too." Obviously, due to budget issues, we couldn't include all the activities, so we selected 60 to make up the guide.

We divided them into learning opening dynamics, activation games, group-building activities, in-depth activities according to the experiential learning cycle, and closing and evaluation dynamics. They are well-detailed, with steps, estimated time, and materials to use. The idea is that anyone who wants to do an environmental education activity or another type of activity can get

inspired, look for ideas, and do activities. We want it to be a helpful guide, not read in one go, but to be consulted continuously.

In addition, the book includes our methodological framework, our principles, the experiential cycle, and how to be a good facilitator. The book has about 14 pages of methodology and facilitation and almost 90 pages of activities and games to be used and reused by whoever needs it.

J: It is fantastic to know that there are these "go-to books" that you can always refer to and that they come from a participatory and collaborative perspective. It is worth noting that collaborating is not just giving instructions; it is building together.

I would like to take advantage of this idea to ask you: How do you see the present and future of environmental education and literacy as a tool for addressing socio-environmental challenges?

N: From my own personal perspective, which I believe is shared by the foundation, I feel that the future of education has to be focused on people, their contexts, their territories, and their realities. We have been using a methodology for centuries that has not changed much, and we see that the path we follow as humanity is not right. There is a lot of individuality, competition, personal interests, and unbridled consumerism, and we have generated all of this through the education we receive.

Education is what makes us who we are, beyond formal education in schools or universities. It is a continuous process. I feel that the path to change has to be through emotional and community ties. We need to understand our territory together, respect and bring all the knowledge we have behind us to the present. These meeting points in diversity generate balance, just as it happens in nature. It is essential that horizontal and respectful dialogue is encouraged. I hope that more people and initiatives adopt this vision to break out of the shell of individuality towards the community towards the shared, which is so beautiful.

MJ: I love listening to Nicole and entirely share her sentiments. I believe education should be transformative; it should awaken people and bring them back to Earth. This can only be achieved by living experiences in connection with nature and our community. We need an education that awakens and transforms, which can only happen from the roots and the people themselves.

J: **Listening to you excites me a lot and makes me think about the challenges involved in creating and proposing an education different from the traditional one. Knowledge must be felt, lived, and seen in and through other people. I think that is the most transformative part of education. Connecting with people is not just about a book or a website but something more profound, and I have loved learning about your story and experiences.**

Would you like to share any final thoughts or comments?

N: For those who receive it and also for those who want to create educational opportunities, it is essential to understand that we have had a European and colonial education for centuries. Although the ideal would be to think of being all together in a forest learning, we will not always be able to do so. Many times, we will be in challenging and restrictive conditions.

The important thing is not to be discouraged by the impossibility of achieving that ideal. Sometimes, small elements or moments can make a difference. For example, if someone makes a mistake, instead of making them feel bad, I tell them: "From this mistake, we can reflect on this or that." Thus, the mistake stops being something negative and becomes an opportunity to reflect. Small changes can reach people and create learning environments.

We will only sometimes have large spaces with many tools, but they are not indispensable for fulfilling the purpose of education. I wish we would get to that point where schools were outdoors, but that is still far off. As you said, many challenges sometimes escape our control. However, let us look for a way to make small changes in the opportunities we have, even if they are restrictive. Even if there are only a few practices, we can always do something.

It is essential to be awake because that is when opportunities arise. It is a matter of taking them, taking advantage of them, and building together. That is why it is a co-construction; we all place a piece in this tower. We should not wait for everything to be ideal to act; small actions add up, everything counts. So, let's not wait to act; let's adapt and move forward little by little.

MJ: I love it because this aligns with what I want to say. Change starts with oneself. On a day-to-day basis, here and now, we decide where we are going. If we want to see a shift in society, the community, or the world, that change must begin with us. The first thing is to make the decision and then take action.

Thank you so much for the invitation and this opportunity. While talking, I remembered the project's beginnings, which was beautiful...Returning to our roots and telling it again.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

The four pillars of education

are aimed at promoting a comprehensive education that encompasses both knowledge and human development.

By Mariana Velázquez

1 Learning to know

Understand and discover to take advantage of the opportunities offered by lifelong education.

2 Learning to do

Confront and resolve conflicts based on experiences, strengthen communication and work with others.

3 Learning to live together

Develop understanding and perception of the forms of interdependence and respect the values of pluralism, mutual understanding, and peace.

4 Learning to be

Contribute to the overall development of each person: body and mind, intelligence, sensitivity, aesthetic sense, and individual responsibility.

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SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

LITERACY AND EDUCATION

By Yanitzi Lorena Morales Fuentes

Literacy

Translation of “literacy” to the Spanish is somewhat complex, as it can be confused with education or teaching basic skills for writing and reading. However, literacy encompasses the **acquisition, use and development** of both oral and written language.

Types of literacy

Critical literacy: ability to select and filter large amounts of information, as well as to analyze its veracity and the ability to contrast sources.

Digital literacy: use of technologies to read and write.

Differences within literacy

Literacy (as learning to read and write) relates to the alphabet and suggests a mechanical view of reading and writing.

But in a wider definition, it involves the social practices mediated by writing and reading and other forms of communication and knowledge.

Literacy in education

Literacy involves understanding and practicing social communication. It is a key component in personal and professional development by acquiring knowledge. In addition, it allows us to know and access information effectively and promotes educational innovation.

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In Mexico, at the national level, 5 out of every 100 inhabitants aged 15 and over cannot read or write.

Data

5%
of people in Mexico do NOT know how to read and write

According to UNESCO (2024), there are 754 million adults in the world who cannot read or write. Two thirds of them are women, as well as 250 million children who do not acquire basic literacy skills.

How to promote literacy?

Early education

Training of personnel capable of teaching reading and writing skills and guiding the development of information interpretation and analysis capabilities.

Use of technology that allows people to become familiar with digital tools that enhance their learning.

Trends

Currently, there is a **gender gap** with a significant difference between the number of women and men who can write, read and have access to information.

Digital education allows for diverse formats and new discursive genres that combine written text, image and sound.

Socioeconomic inequalities have a great impact on a person's ability to learn and build knowledge.

Multiliteracy allows people to develop the ability to read, write, analyze, and interpret information from different texts and media.

It is increasingly necessary for people to have a **basic understanding of science** to address issues such as climate change, pandemics, or sustainability.

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In the material we recommend to complement this issue, we explore tools and resources that promote literacy in sustainability issues. Each resource is designed to foster a deeper and more respectful understanding of nature and the generation of new ways of becoming aware and acting in the face of current socio-environmental challenges, ranging from free-air learning experiences to using video games to detonate the reflection.

Guideline to activities for environmental education

This guideline, published by Fundación El Árbol, is a compilation of collaborative experiences to learn about nature that systematizes the work of the “Red de Restauradores” project. It seeks to transmit its ten-year experience with environmental education based on significant experiences.

https://fundacionelarbol.cl/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/GUIAEDUCATIVA_web1.pdf

You can check out more publications from the El Árbol Foundation at the following link:
<https://fundacionelarbol.cl/publicaciones/>

Videogame: *Carbon counts*

This project focuses on the power of play to change the world. It is an incredibly fun game that seeks to have a real and lasting impact. Together, the gaming experiences developed by its creators have engaged more than 500 million players worldwide and have generated billions of dollars invested in reforestation projects and reinvested to continue generating these learning and awareness tools. You can download the game at the following link:

<https://www.carboncounts.tech/>

Podcast: *The challenges of environmental education*

This episode of the podcast “The Great Socio-Environmental Challenges” from the University Coordination for Sustainability addresses the topic of environmental education. In it, several experts talk about the complex relationships between human beings and the environment, as well as what is needed to understand them through experiences in environmental education and the challenges they face.

<https://open.spotify.com/episode/3SCk79kXn6VeUmAcM0mIP?si=d1827d6a42f345ba>

Full seminar here:
<https://www.youtube.com/live/-BTGvG1wiKo?feature=share>

Forest School for Outdoor and Woodland Learning

Forest School is a long-term development program that runs regularly for a minimum of 6 sessions, usually once a week. This program is dedicated to increasing the use of Scotland's outdoor environments for learning to expand learning experiences for sustainability, improving health and wellbeing through outdoor activities, and growing understanding of natural environments.

<https://owlsotland.org/woodland-learning/forest-school/>

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

Carbon Literacy Project

This program offers a day of learning on carbon literacy, covering climate change, carbon footprint, and how we can all contribute to controlling carbon emissions. The program provides a wide range of tools on the topic and certification.

<https://carbonliteracy.com/>

The Handbook of Sustainability Literacy

This book, edited by Arran Stibbe, features a range of people with very diverse approaches to sustainability – transition skills, complexity, permaculture, common thinking, or the concept of effortless action (wu wei). Each short chapter is accompanied by ideas, learning exercises, or ways to help “land” these skills.

<https://sustainability.glos.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Handbk-Sustainability-literacy-EC-16092020.pdf>

Film: *Baraka*

A non-dialogue documentary that explores the tensions between nature and human activity. This work invites reflection on the impact of civilization on the environment. It connects with issues of sustainability literacy by looking at the need to understand and act on the ecological, cultural, and social challenges we face as humanity.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jd-ZXU4hgEE>

Videogame: *Eco*

It is a multiplayer simulation video game (released in 2018) in which collaboration is essential to build and manage a civilization in a virtual but realistic environment. The objective is to develop sustainable systems to meet the population's needs without causing irreversible damage. The decisions directly affect the ecosystem, so they must balance economic development with the conservation of natural resources and pollution reduction.

<https://play.eco/>